

THE LOG-BALANCEDNESS OF THE SEQUENCE FOR THE ALTERNATING SUMS OF MOTZKIN NUMBERS

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Received: 1/1/26, Accepted: 4/9/26, Published: 5/1/26

Abstract

Let {M_n}_{n>=0} be the Motzkin sequence. For n >= 0, put T_n = sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} M_k. The main purpose of this paper is to study the log-behavior of the sequence {T_n}_{n>=0}. We show that {T_n}_{n>=8} is log-balanced. In addition, we discuss the log-behavior of some sequences involving T_n. For instance, we prove that the sequence {M_n + T_n}_{n>=6} is log-balanced.

1. Introduction

Let {M_n}_{n>=0} denote the Motzkin sequence in this paper. The Motzkin sequence {M_n}_{n>=0} is sequence A001006 in the OEIS [9] and satisfies the recurrence relation

(n + 3)M_{n+1} = (2n + 3)M_n + 3nM_{n-1}, (1)

with the initial conditions M_0 = 1 and M_1 = 1. Some values of {M_n}_{n>=0} are listed in Table 1. The Motzkin numbers play an important role in enumerative

Table with 2 rows and 13 columns. Row 1: n | 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12. Row 2: M_n | 1 1 2 4 9 21 51 127 323 835 2188 5798 15511

Table 1: Some values of {M_n}_{n>=0}

combinatorics. The value of M_n is the number of lattice paths from (0, 0) to (n, n), with steps (0, 2), (2, 0, and (1, 1), never rising above the line y = x. Consider the sequence for the alternating sums of Motzkin numbers. For n >= 0, let

T_n = sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} M_k. (2)

The sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A187306 in the OEIS [9] and some values of $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ are given in Table 2. The value of T_n is the number of simple permutations

n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
T_n	1	0	2	2	7	14	37	90	233	602	1586	4212	11299

Table 2: Some values of $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$

of each length that avoid the pattern 321 (i.e., are the union of two increasing sequences, and in one line notation contain no nontrivial block of values which form an interval). Let $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be the sequence of Riordan numbers. The sequence $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A005043 in the OEIS [9] and the value of r_n is the number of Dyck paths of semilength n with no peaks at odd level. There is an identity between $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, which is

$$T_n = r_{n+1} + (-1)^n. \tag{3}$$

For more properties of $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, see sequence A187306 in the OEIS [9]. In this paper, we investigate some properties of $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$.

Now we recall some definitions. A sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ of positive numbers is called *log-convex* (*log-concave*) if $z_n^2 \leq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$ ($z_n^2 \geq z_{n-1}z_{n+1}$) for each $n \geq 1$. A log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is called *log-balanced* if $\{\frac{z_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-concave (Došlić [3] gave this definition). A sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ of positive numbers is *tempered* (see Došlić [7]) if its quotient sequence $x_n = \frac{z_{n+1}}{z_n}$ satisfies

$$\frac{n}{n+1}x_{n-1} \leq x_n \leq \frac{n+1}{n}x_{n-1}.$$

It is known that a sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex (log-concave) if and only if its quotient sequence $\{\frac{z_{n+1}}{z_n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nondecreasing (nonincreasing) and a log-convex sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-balanced if and only if $\{\frac{z_{n+1}}{(n+1)z_n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is nonincreasing. It is clear that a log-balanced sequence is tempered. Log-convexity (Log-concavity) is not only instrumental in obtaining the growth rate and asymptotic behavior of a sequence, but also a fertile source of combinatorial inequalities. In addition, log-convexity (log-concavity) plays an important role in many subjects (see for instance [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10]). Log-balancedness can help us find more inequalities. Many combinatorial sequences, including the Motzkin numbers, the large Schröder numbers, the central Delannoy numbers, and the Bell numbers are log-balanced. One can find more log-balanced sequences in Došlić [3]. Log-balanced sequences play an important role in other subjects. For instance, Bell numbers provide important examples in white noise distribution theory (for more details, see Asai et al. [1]). This paper is concerned with the log-balancedness of $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$. In addition, we also discuss the log-behavior of some sequences related to $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$.

2. Main Results

Došlić [3] proved that the Motzkin sequence $\{M_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-balanced. Now we discuss the log-balancedness of the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2).

Theorem 1. *For the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2), $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-balanced and $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 5}$ is tempered.*

Proof. It follows from (2) that the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfies the recurrence relation

$$T_{n+1} = \left(\frac{M_{n+1}}{M_n} - 1 \right) T_n + \frac{M_{n+1}}{M_n} T_{n-1}. \tag{4}$$

For $n \geq 0$, let $x_n = \frac{M_{n+1}}{M_n}$ and $y_n = \frac{T_{n+1}}{T_n}$ ($n \geq 2$). By (1), we have that the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ satisfies the recurrence relation

$$x_n = \frac{2n + 3}{n + 3} + \frac{3n}{(n + 3)x_{n-1}}. \tag{5}$$

It follows from (4) that

$$y_n = x_n - 1 + \frac{x_n}{y_{n-1}} \quad \text{for } n \geq 3. \tag{6}$$

In order to prove that the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-balanced, we need to show that $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is increasing and $\{\frac{y_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 8}$ is decreasing. Now we prove by induction that

$$x_n \leq y_n \leq x_{n+1} \quad \text{for } n \geq 9. \tag{7}$$

We observe that $x_k < y_k < x_{k+1}$ for $k = 9, 10$. Assume that $x_k \leq y_k \leq x_{k+1}$ for $k \geq 10$. By applying (6), we have

$$y_{k+1} - x_{k+1} = -1 + \frac{x_{k+1}}{y_k}$$

and

$$y_{k+1} - x_{k+2} = x_{k+1} - 1 + \frac{x_{k+1}}{y_k} - x_{k+2}.$$

For $k \geq 10$, noting that $x_k \leq y_k \leq x_{k+1}$, we obtain $y_{k+1} - x_{k+1} \geq 0$ and

$$y_{k+1} - x_{k+2} \leq x_{k+1} - 1 + \frac{x_{k+1}}{x_k} - x_{k+2}.$$

By means of (5), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x_{k+1} - 1 - x_{k+2} &= x_{k+1} - 1 - \frac{2k + 7}{k + 5} - \frac{3(k + 2)}{(k + 5)x_{k+1}} \\ &= \frac{2k + 5}{k + 4} + \frac{3(k + 1)}{(k + 4)x_k} - 1 - \frac{2k + 7}{k + 5} - \frac{3(k + 2)(k + 4)x_k}{(k + 5)[(2k + 5)x_k + 3(k + 1)]} \\ &= -\frac{k^2 + 9k + 23}{(k + 4)(k + 5)} + \frac{3(k + 1)}{(k + 4)x_k} - \frac{3(k + 2)(k + 4)x_k}{(k + 5)[(2k + 5)x_k + 3(k + 1)]} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{x_{k+1}}{x_k} = \frac{2k+5}{(k+4)x_k} + \frac{3(k+1)}{(k+4)x_k^2}.$$

Došlić [6] proved that

$$b_n \leq x_n \leq b_{n+1} \quad \text{for } n \geq 2, \tag{8}$$

where $b_n = \frac{6(n+1)}{2n+5}$. By using (8), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x_{k+1} - 1 - x_{k+2} &\leq -\frac{k^2+9k+23}{(k+4)(k+5)} + \frac{3(k+1)}{(k+4)b_k} - \frac{3(k+2)(k+4)b_k}{(k+5)[(2k+5)b_k+3(k+1)]} \\ &= -2 - \frac{3}{(k+4)(k+5)} + \frac{2k+5}{2(k+4)} + \frac{3(k+3)}{(k+5)(2k+5)} \\ &= -\frac{2k+11}{2(k+4)} - \frac{3}{(k+4)(k+5)} + \frac{3(k+3)}{(k+5)(2k+5)} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x_{k+1}}{x_k} &\leq \frac{2k+5}{(k+4)b_k} + \frac{3(k+1)}{(k+4)b_k^2} \\ &= 1 + \frac{9}{4(k+1)(k+4)}. \end{aligned}$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} y_{k+1} - x_{k+2} &\leq -\frac{3}{2(k+4)} - \frac{3}{(k+4)(k+5)} + \frac{9}{4(k+1)(k+4)} + \frac{3(k+3)}{(k+5)(2k+5)} \\ &= -\frac{3(k+1)}{2(k+4)(k+5)(2k+5)} - \frac{3(k-11)}{4(k+1)(k+4)(k+5)} \\ &= -\frac{3(4k^2-13k-53)}{4(k+1)(k+4)(k+5)(2k+5)} < 0 \quad \text{for } k \geq 10. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that the sequence $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 9}$ is increasing. On the other hand, we observe that $y_8 < y_9$. Thus, the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-convex. Now we prove that the sequence $\{\frac{y_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is decreasing. By using (7) and (8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} (n+2)y_n - (n+1)y_{n+1} &\geq (n+2)x_n - (n+1)x_{n+2} \\ &\geq (n+2)b_n - (n+1)b_{n+3} \\ &= \frac{6(n+1)(n+2)}{2n+5} - \frac{6(n+1)(n+4)}{2n+11} \\ &= \frac{12(n+1)^2}{(2n+5)(2n+11)} > 0 \quad \text{for } n \geq 9. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the sequence $\{\frac{y_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is decreasing. On the other hand, it is clear that $y_8 < y_9$ and $\frac{y_8}{9} > \frac{y_9}{10}$. Then $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is increasing and $\{\frac{y_n}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 8}$ is decreasing.

Because the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-balanced, $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is tempered. On the other hand, we observe that $\{T_k\}_{5 \leq k \leq 9}$ is tempered. Then $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 5}$ is tempered. \square

Corollary 1. *For the sequence of Riordan numbers $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, $\{r_{2n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex.*

Proof. We have that $r_{2n+2} = T_{2n+1} + 1$ from (3). It follows from Theorem 1 that the sequence $\{T_{2n+1}\}_{n \geq 4}$ is log-convex. Then $\{r_{2n+2}\}_{n \geq 4}$ is log-convex. On the other hand, we find that $\{r_{2k}\}_{0 \leq k \leq 5}$ is log-convex. Thus, the sequence $\{r_{2n}\}_{n \geq 0}$ is log-convex. □

Theorem 2. *For the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2), $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 6}$ is log-convex and $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-balanced.*

Proof. It follows from the log-convexity of the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ that $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-convex. We observe that $\{T_j T_{j+1}\}_{6 \leq j \leq 9}$ is log-convex. Thus, the sequence $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 6}$ is log-convex. For $n \geq 9$, let $x_n = \frac{M_{n+1}}{M_n}$ and $y_n = \frac{T_{n+1}}{T_n}$. It is evident that $\{y_n y_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is the quotient sequence of $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$. We find that

$$\frac{y_n y_{n+1}}{n+1} - \frac{y_{n+1} y_{n+2}}{n+2} = \frac{(n+2)y_n - (n+1)y_{n+2}}{(n+1)(n+2)} y_{n+1}.$$

It follows from (7) and (8) that

$$\begin{aligned} (n+2)y_n - (n+1)y_{n+2} &\geq (n+2)x_n - (n+1)x_{n+3} \\ &\geq (n+2)b_n - (n+1)b_{n+4} \\ &= \frac{6(n+1)(2n+1)}{(2n+5)(2n+13)} > 0 \quad (n \geq 9). \end{aligned}$$

This means that the sequence $\{\frac{y_n y_{n+1}}{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is decreasing. Thus, $\{T_n T_{n+1}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-balanced. □

Theorem 3. *For the Motzkin sequence $\{M_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2), $\{M_n + T_n\}_{n \geq 6}$ is log-balanced.*

Proof. It follows from the log-convexity of the sequences $\{M_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 9}$ that $\{M_n + T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-convex. Now we prove that the sequence $\{\frac{M_n + T_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-concave. For $n \geq 9$, let $x_n = \frac{M_{n+1}}{M_n}$ and $y_n = \frac{T_{n+1}}{T_n}$. For $n \geq 10$, put

$$\Psi_n = (n+1)(M_n + T_n)^2 - n(M_{n-1} + T_{n-1})(M_{n+1} + T_{n+1}).$$

In order to prove that the sequence $\{\frac{M_n + T_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-concave, we only need to show that $\Psi_n \geq 0$ for $n \geq 10$. It is obvious that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_n &= (n+1)M_n^2 - nM_{n-1}M_{n+1} + (n+1)T_n^2 - nT_{n-1}T_{n+1} \\ &\quad + 2(n+1)M_n T_n - nM_{n-1}T_{n+1} - nM_{n+1}T_{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from the log-balancedness of the sequences $\{M_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ and $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ that

$$(n + 1)M_n^2 - nM_{n-1}M_{n+1} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (n + 1)T_n^2 - nT_{n-1}T_{n+1} \geq 0.$$

Then we have

$$\Psi_n \geq 2(n + 1)M_nT_n - nM_{n-1}T_{n+1} - nM_{n+1}T_{n-1}.$$

We note that

$$\Psi_n \geq M_{n-1}T_{n-1}[2(n + 1)x_{n-1}y_{n-1} - ny_{n-1}y_n - nx_{n-1}x_n].$$

By applying (7) and (8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_n &\geq M_{n-1}T_{n-1}[2(n + 1)x_{n-1}^2 - nx_nx_{n+1} - nx_{n-1}x_n] \\ &\geq M_{n-1}T_{n-1}[2(n + 1)b_{n-1}^2 - nb_{n+1}b_{n+2} - nb_nb_{n+1}] \\ &\geq 2M_{n-1}T_{n-1}[(n + 1)b_{n-1}^2 - nb_{n+2}^2] \\ &= 2M_{n-1}T_{n-1} \left[\frac{36(n + 1)n^2}{(2n + 3)^2} - \frac{36n(n + 3)^2}{(2n + 9)^2} \right] \\ &= \frac{72nM_{n-1}T_{n-1}(4n^3 - 81n - 81)}{(2n + 3)^2(2n + 9)^2} > 0 \quad \text{for } n \geq 10. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the sequence $\{M_n + T_n\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-balanced. On the other hand, we observe that $\{M_k + T_k\}_{6 \leq k \leq 10}$ is log-balanced. Then the sequence $\{M_n + T_n\}_{n \geq 6}$ is log-balanced. \square

For the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ of the alternating sums of Motzkin numbers, we proved that $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 5}$ is tempered. In the final of this section, we consider the alternating sums of Fibonacci numbers F_n . For $n \geq 0$, let

$$W_n = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} F_k. \tag{9}$$

The sequence $\{(-1)^n W_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is sequence A119282 in the OEIS [9]. For $n \geq 1$, the closed form of $(-1)^n W_n$ is (see sequence A119282 in the OEIS [9])

$$(-1)^n W_n = (-1)^n F_{n-1} - 1.$$

For $n \geq 1$, it is evident that

$$W_n = F_{n-1} - (-1)^n. \tag{10}$$

Some values of $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ are given in Table 3.

n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
W_n	0	1	0	2	1	4	4	9	12	22	33	56	88	145	232

Table 3: Some values of $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 0}$

Now we prove that the sequence $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is tempered.

Theorem 4. *For the sequence $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (9), $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is tempered.*

Proof. In order to prove that the sequence $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is tempered, we only need to show that $\{\frac{W_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 11}$ is log-concave and $\{n!W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is log-convex. The sequence $\{\frac{W_n}{n!}\}_{n \geq 11}$ is log-concave if and only if $(n+1)W_n^2 - nW_{n-1}W_{n+1} \geq 0$ for $n \geq 12$, and the sequence $\{n!W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is log-convex if and only if $nW_n^2 - (n+1)W_{n-1}W_{n+1} \leq 0$ for $n \geq 12$. For convenience, set

$$\Sigma_n = (n+1)W_n^2 - nW_{n-1}W_{n+1} \quad \text{and} \quad \Omega_n = nW_n^2 - (n+1)W_{n-1}W_{n+1}.$$

It follows from (10) that

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_n &= (n+1)[F_{n-1} - (-1)^n]^2 - n[F_{n-2} - (-1)^{n-1}][F_n - (-1)^{n+1}] \\ &= n(F_{n-1}^2 - F_{n-2}F_n) + F_{n-1}^2 - 2(-1)^n F_{n-1} - (-1)^n n(2F_{n-1} + F_{n-2} + F_n) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_n &= n[F_{n-1} - (-1)^n]^2 - (n+1)[F_{n-2} - (-1)^{n-1}][F_n - (-1)^{n+1}] \\ &= n(F_{n-1}^2 - F_{n-2}F_n) - F_{n-2}F_n - (-1)^n(F_{n-2} + F_n) \\ &\quad - (-1)^n n(2F_{n-1} + F_{n-2} + F_n) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Applying $F_{n-1}^2 - F_{n-2}F_n = (-1)^n$ and

$$F_{n+1} = F_n + F_{n-1}, \tag{11}$$

we obtain

$$\Sigma_n = (-1)^n n + F_{n-1}^2 - 2(-1)^n F_{n-1} - (-1)^n n F_{n+2} + 1$$

and

$$\Omega_n = (-1)^n n - F_{n-2}F_n - (-1)^n(F_{n-2} + F_n) - (-1)^n n F_{n+2} - 1.$$

It is obvious that

$$\Sigma_n \geq F_{n-1}^2 - 2F_{n-1} - nF_{n+2} - n + 1$$

and

$$\Omega_n \leq n - F_{n-2}F_n + 2F_n + nF_{n+2} - 1.$$

We observe that $\Sigma_{12} > 0$ and $\Omega_{12} < 0$. For $n \geq 13$, one can prove by induction that

$$F_{n-1} - 2 > 7n \tag{12}$$

and

$$F_{n-2} - 2 \geq 6n \tag{13}$$

By using (11)–(13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_n &> 7nF_{n-1} - nF_{n+2} - n + 1 = 6nF_{n-1} - 2nF_n - n + 1 \\ &= 2nF_{n-1} + 2nF_{n-3} - n + 1 > 3n + 1 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_n &\leq n - 6nF_n + nF_{n+2} - 1 = n - 5nF_n + nF_{n+1} - 1 \\ &= n - 4nF_n + nF_{n-1} - 1 < n - 3nF_n - 1 < -2n - 1 < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Then the sequence $\{W_n\}_{n \geq 11}$ is tempered. □

3. Concluding Remarks

For the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2), we mainly proved that $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 8}$ is log-balanced. In addition, we also discussed the log-behavior of some sequences involving T_n . For $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$, we now give a conjecture.

Conjecture 1. For the sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ defined by (2), $\{\sqrt[n]{T_n}\}_{n \geq 9}$ is log-concave.

Acknowledgment. The author would like to thank the referee for providing valuable suggestions.

References

- [1] N. Asai, I. Kubo, and H.-H. Kuo, Bell numbers, log-concavity, and log-convexity, *Acta Appl. Math.* **63** (1–3) (2000), 79–87.
- [2] F. Brenti, Log-concave and unimodal sequences in algebra, combinatorics, and geometry: An update, *Contemp. Math.* **178** (1994), 71–89.

- [3] T. Došlić, Log-balanced combinatorial sequences, *Int. J. Math. Math. Sci.* **4** (2005), 507–522.
- [4] T. Došlić, Seven (lattice) paths to log-convexity, *Acta Appl. Math.* **110** (3) (2010), 1373–1392.
- [5] T. Došlić, D. Svrtan, and D. Veljan, Enumerative aspects of secondary structures, *Discrete Math.* **285** (1–3) (2004), 67–82.
- [6] T. Došlić and D. Veljan, Logarithmic behavior of some combinatorial sequences, *Discrete Math.* **308** (11) (2008), 2182–2212.
- [7] T. Došlić and B. Kolarec, On log-definite tempered combinatorial sequences, *Mathematics* **13** (2025), 1179.
- [8] O. Milenkovic and K.J. Compton, Probabilistic transforms for combinatorial urn models, *Combin. Probab. Comput.* **13** (4–5) (2004), 645–675.
- [9] OEIS Foundation Inc., The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <https://oeis.org>.
- [10] R.P. Stanley, *Log-concave and unimodal sequences in algebra, combinatorics, and geometry*, Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, **576** (1989), 500–535.